

An Updated Checklist of Polychaetes (Annelida: Polychaeta) from Karwar Coast

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Abstract

The present checklist of benthic macro polychaetes from three zones of Karwar was reviewed based on the recent surveys and published literature. Total 60 species belonging to 30 families were found to be mixed with valid names and hence revised checklist is prepared. The dominant families observed were Nereidae, Spionidae, Cossuridae, Eunicidae, Glycereidae, Capitellidae and Sabellaridae. The current literature includes checklist and distributional records of phylum Annelida, polychaeta from three zones of Karwar coast. The species names arranged alphabetically, providing a valid scientific name with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS), Marine Species Identification Portal, Bio search Marine Biodiversity Database of India, World Polychaete Database.

Key words: Coastal ecosystem, Benthos, Macro polychaetes, Revised study, Taxonomy

Introduction

The polychaetes are the dominant benthic macro faunal community in the marine ecosystem, from the intertidal areas down to the deep sea. Most of the species are measured to 5 to 10 cm quite smaller and short lived exhibiting a higher secondary production. Hence they are an important link in marine food webs and feature significantly in the diets of many bottom feeders (Ajmal Khan, 2005; Balkrishnan, 2019). Polychaetes play a vital role in ecosystem process such nutrients recycling, degradation of pollutants, dispersal of organic matters and besides enhancing secondary production (Snelgrove, 1998). Polychaetes are an important component in marine food chain especially for benthic fishes and other bottom feeders (Parulekar, 1982; Herman, 2000). They dominate the macro benthic community in terms of distribution, abundance and biomass. In this way polychaetes play a significant role in the stability and function of benthic ecosystem. Polychaetes are indicators of healthy aquatic ecosystem and some species are known to signify as pollution indicators. The first monograph on Indian polychaetes fauna of India including Pakistan, Cylone, Burma and Malaya. Annelida polychaeta was published by Fauvel (Fauvel, 1953). Reviews and checklists from different coastal regions continued to be published during the previous years (Ajmal Khan., 2005, Sivaleela G, 2012, Pati S, 2015). Regional checklists have been published at regular intervals throughout the decades. A perusal of types of the literature revealed that research on diversity and distribution of polychaetes from different coastal ecosystems of India has got maximum attention (Harkantra, 1985; Pillai, 2001; Balakrishnan, 2018). No comprehensive study has been undertaken so far on benthic biodiversity in general and polychaete taxonomy, particularly in the Karwar coast. The present study aims to compile an annotated checklist of the polychaetes from Karwar coast based on the literature available at different source and recent collections made during the regular survey and to list suggestions for future taxonomical polychaete research.

Materials and Methods

The present study was carried out from 3 zones, two from inshore waters and one from estuarine zones of Karwar coast of Uttar Kannada, Karnataka. The sediment samples were collected at the depths of 5, 10, 15mtrs from each station. The Peterson's grab (0.1m² (0.1m²×10=1m²)) were used for collecting the sediment samples. The sediment samples after sieving through 500 micron mesh sieve the polychaetes specimens were preserved in 5% formalin. (Day, 1967 a, b and c) keys were used for taxonomic identification of polychaetes. The checklist for the polychaete species reported from the different zones of

Karwar coastal ecosystem were made following complete bibliographic review and analysis of published articles, monographs, catalogues, checklist and website reports. Species names recorded in the literature were validated with WoRMS and polychaete database and all corrected names were revised and restructured checklists have been prepared.

Fig.1 Map: Location of the study zones in the Karwar coast (Arabian Sea) and Kali estuary, Karnataka

Results:

Table 1. Checklist of benthic macro polychaetes of Karwar (* = Present; - = Absent)

Sl. No.	Family	Species	Zone1	Zone2	Zone 3
1	Nereidae	<i>Ceratonereis (Compositia) costae</i>	*	*	*
2		<i>Dendronereides heteropoda</i>	-	-	*
3		<i>Neanthes zonata</i>	*	*	-
4		<i>Nereis pelagica</i>	*	*	*
5		<i>Perinereis cultrifera</i>	*	*	*
6		<i>Platynereis dumerilii</i>	*	*	*
7	Lumbrineridae	<i>Kuwaita heteropoda</i>	*	*	*
8		<i>Lumbrineris polydesma</i>	*	-	*
9		<i>Lumbrineris japonica</i>	*	*	*
10	Capitellidae	<i>Capitella capitata</i>	*	*	*
11		<i>Heteromastus filiformis</i>	*	*	*
12		<i>Mediomastus capensis</i>	*	*	*
13		<i>Notomastus latericeus</i>	*	*	*
14	Glyceridae	<i>Glycera alba</i>	*	*	*
15	Cossuridae	<i>Cossura coasta</i>	*	*	*
16	Magelonidae	<i>Magelona papillicornis</i>	*	*	-
17	Eunicidae	<i>Eunice indica</i>	*	*	*
18		<i>Eunice tubifex</i>	*	-	*

19		<i>Diopatra cuprea</i>	*	*	*
20		<i>Marphysa sanguinea</i>	*	*	*
21	Spionidae	<i>Malacoceros indicus</i>	*	*	*
22		<i>Prionospio</i> sp.	*	-	-
23		<i>Paraprionospio</i> sp.	*	*	*
24		<i>Polydora ciliata</i>	*	*	*
25		<i>Prionospio cirrifera</i>	*	*	*
26		<i>Paraprionospio pinnata</i>	*	*	*
27		<i>Prionospio heterobranchia</i>	*	-	*
28	Nephtyidae	<i>Nephtys polybranchia</i>	*	-	*
29	Cirratulidae	<i>Chaetozone setosa</i>	*	*	-
30		<i>Cirratulus cirratus</i>	*	*	-
31		<i>Aphelochaeta filibranchia</i>	*	*	*
32	Pilargidae	<i>Sigambra constricta</i>	*	*	*
33	Paraonidae	<i>Aricidea (Acmira) lopezi</i>	*	*	-
34	Onuphidae	<i>Onuphis eremita</i>	*	*	*
35	Maldanidae	<i>Maldanella capensis</i>	*	*	*
36	Syllidae	<i>Exogone verugera</i>	*	*	*
37		<i>Odontosyllis polycera</i>	*	*	-
38		<i>Syllis gracilis</i>	*	-	*
39	Phyllodocidae	<i>Eteone longa</i>	*	-	*
40		<i>Phyllodoce rosea</i>	*	*	*
41	Ampharetidae	<i>Amphicteis gunneri</i>	*	-	*
42	Hesionidae	<i>Hesion</i> sp.	*	*	*
43		<i>Leocrates claparedii</i>	*	*	*
44	Oweniidae	<i>Owenia fusiformis</i>	*	*	*
45	Chaetopteridae	<i>Mesochaetopterus minutus</i>	*	*	-
46	Sabellariidae	<i>Sabellaria spinulosa</i>	*	*	*
47	Sternapsidae	<i>Sternaspis scutata</i>	*	-	*
48	Serpulidae	<i>Serpula vermicularis</i>	*	-	*
49	Opheliidae	<i>Armandia lanceolata</i>	*	*	*
50	Amphinomidae	<i>Eurythoe complanata</i>	*	-	*
51	Aphroditidae	<i>Lepidonotus squamatus</i>	*	-	*
52		<i>Sthenelais boa</i>	*	*	*
53		<i>Macellicephal</i> <i>mirabilis</i>	*	*	-
54	Orbiniidae	<i>Scoloplos armiger</i>	*	*	*
55	Goniadidae	<i>Glycinde oligodon</i>	*	-	*
56		<i>Goniada emerita</i>	*	*	*
57	Pisionidae	<i>Pisione remota</i>	*	-	-
58	Terebellidae	<i>Pista cristata</i>	*	-	-
59		<i>Terebella ehrenbergi</i>	*	*	*
60		<i>Terebellides stroemii</i>	*	*	*

The updated checklist of polychaetes from three zones of Karwar is presented in Table 1 includes the accepted names, authors, locality and distribution information followed by references. The updated checklist was prepared by enlisting species only with the valid names.

The updated checklist was prepared by enlisting species only with the valid names. The list comprised 60 species belonging to 9 orders, 30 families of polychaetes from Karwar coast (Table 1). The analysis based on the dominant family wise contribution of some species related were represented that Capitellidae, Nereidae, Spionidae, Eunicidae, Magelonidae, Lumbrinereidae, Cirratulidae, Pilargidae and Aphroditidae. The major family of Nereidae was represented by 6 species belonging to 6 different genera. The macro polychaetes distribution is organised into three different sampling zones and thus a total of 59, 44 and 49 species were recorded from Zone 1, Zone 2 and Zone 3 respectively. The species from the families Nereidae, Capitellidae, Magelonidae, Eunicidae, Spionidae, Syllidae, Hesionidae and Glycereidae were represented uniformly from all the study zones. The species found in estuary are Sabellaridae, Terebellidae, Goniadidae and Nepthyidae. (Fig.2).

Fig.2.-Zone wise and Family wise contribution of number of species of Phylum polychaetes reported from Karwar coast.

Discussion

The checklist presented in this study represents the updated list of marine and estuarine polychaetes recorded from the Karwar coast. The updated information based on species occurrence data recorded 60 species belonging to 9 orders, 30 families of polychaetes so far reported from Karwar coastal water (Tab.1) within the recorded polychaetes families the Spionidae family was found to be most diverse family followed by Nereidae. Fauvel reported about 450 species of polychaetes in and around coastal waters and stated that this was probably half of the total number occurring in the Indian coastal region. The 48 species of polychaetes recorded from Puri, Konark, Chandipuri coasts of Orissa from Misra (1984, 1987) and 107 species belonging to 28 families of polychaetes from Chandbali, Bhitarkannika and Talichua ecosystem. There is no updated publication on marine annelids from this region. There is limited work to updated the checklist of marine annelids in the country. Sivleela and Venkatraman (2012) 330 species of benthic polychaetes belonging to 66 families under 163 genera from Indian coast. The present study indicates higher polychaete diversity as compared to earlier reports. Earlier 53 species of polychaetes, of which 34 species belong to macro and 19 species to meio polychaetes have been recorded from Karwar Bay by Sudarshan (1983). Musale and Desai (2011) reported 38 species of polychaetes showed higher abundance along the west coast, whereas 25 species showed higher abundance along east coast In the present study 60 polychaetes species were identified, thus indicating that the Karwar inshore and estuarine areas holds

diverse macro benthic polychaetes fauna. The updated checklists provided here may be considered as the baseline evidence for additional explorations as it was compiled to update the polychaete species list Karwar coast for future reference. The updated checklist hopes to encourage national and international interest in improving accuracy of Indian regional taxonomy and new revisionary studies. The present checklist of polychaetes species is baseline data intended to guide systematic work in this area.

Conclusion

The present study focused to assess the updated checklist of polychaete taxon, its diversity and abundance along the Karwar coast. The present study focused on the 60 species of polychaetes along the inshore and estuarine areas of Karwar coast. The estuarine area of Karwar supports the diversity of polychaetes. The dominant distributed families were Capitellidae, Nereidae, Spionidae, Eunicidae, Magelonidae, Lumbrinereidae, Cirratulidae, Pilargidae and Aphroditidae.

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